

THE PROBLEM OF CREATIVITY AND ITS FORMATION IN YOUNG PEOPLE

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Abstract. *Through this article, the author expressed his opinion about the characteristics of creative thinking of young people in finding their place in society and their self-awareness and the unconventionality of the thinking process, some features of its formation.*

Keywords: *youth, self-awareness, creativity, thinking, social relations, unconventionality of thinking, ability, innovation, compositional, critical and technical culture, socio-economic changes.*

In the world psychoanalytical practice, the strategic understanding of social self-behavior as an internal spiritual management of young people, the study of the problem of forming a mind capable of independence and responsibility in them shows that it is a particularly urgent issue in the current complex socio-economic changes. In the conditions of social changes, great attention is being paid to the problems of developing thinking by developing the social skills of young people, forming innovative, creative, compositional, critical and technical culture.

In particular, improving the technology of developing spiritual and moral social competence as a factor of socialization of young people, improving the technology of neurolinguistic programming aimed at supporting their social activity and initiative, improvement of psychological-pedagogical mechanisms of creative culture development is emerging as one of the most urgent issues of today. At the same time, creativity acts as the supreme manager of human activity and directs it towards good deeds. Such a creative person always acts in harmony with existence.

Creativity in youth is a social self-management and organization that defines the needs of society and creates social spaces for different levels of creativity. The need for creativity is unique to every person, but its organization at the level of social spaces, specific, spontaneous, self-regulating social values creates certain limitations in raising the creative abilities of young people to the highest level.

As a result, only some representatives of people and young people reach this level based on their individual characteristics, while others, facing social competition, seek and find their own development paths in other social spaces, because society needs people with constant creative qualities.

Based on the characteristics of this need, we can say that people, especially young people, need to be understood as carriers of changes in society. Improvement of all aspects of personality and youth development is related to the changes taking place in science and technology, which requires continuous improvement of the level of knowledge of each person.

It shows how careful and responsible attention should be paid to all the mechanisms connected in one way or another with the formation of personality, which is the most complex of all types of social production today. The problem of conscious and professional selection of future artists is the problem of a creative school that creates creativity in young people.

Self-awareness of young people reflects the transition from individualization of socialization to socialization of the individual.

Currently, the problem of socialization of an individual is taking on a complex character at the intersection of various fields of knowledge. In modern sociology, philosophy, political science, psychology, cultural studies, "socialization" means the process of assimilation and active repetition of social norms and cultural values of the society to which a person belongs.

American sociologist F. G. Giddings, the author of the term "socialization" applied to a person, explained in his "Theory of Socialization" that it is "the development of the social nature or character of the person", "the preparation of human potential for social life."

The development of almost all areas of human activity constantly needs people who perceive the surrounding world in a non-standard and unequal way, who are extremely active, capable of working, and who can achieve high results in their chosen field of activity.

On the one hand, these features expand the possibilities of self-realization of a person in all spheres of activity, and on the other hand, modern conditions require independent decision-making, development and implementation of ideas without patterns, absorption of acquired knowledge into other spheres of life, behavior in solving various problems. puts high demands on the state of changing tactics.

This all characteristics depend on the quality of creativity of people, which is directly related to general psychological knowledge.

The most important thing for a person is his spiritual self-realization, because the "I" of a person is related to his freedom and harmony of spirituality. According to modern research scientists of human psychology, the main feature of leading thinking recognizes that it originates from the principle of opposition between the subject and the object.

Man realizes himself as a being and at the same time has freedom. The freedom of the individual consists not in the fact that he is formed by natural or social necessity, but that he "knows" himself and shapes himself with every action and deed. As a result, a free person is responsible for everything he does and does not justify his actions with "conditions" and finds his place in life on this basis.

As noted in dozens of works of the world-known and famous Eastern scholars (Forabi, Beruni, Ibn Sina, Ulugbek, Navoi, Abdullah Avloni, etc.), already in the Middle Ages, especially in our Central Asian regions, the level of intellectual development, primary knowledge and skills of young people, profession or special attention is paid to the preparation of young people for the future life, taking into account the manifestation of their inner attitude and inclination to a particular type of art.

Young people with creative characteristics show uncompromising, conflicting, high emotionality in life. They solve internal problems independently. Normal-minded young people do not show high emotionality and do not approve of it. As they answer questions about their future careers, they discuss the creative nature of work, the pursuit of excellence, and attraction to non-traditional activities. They want to contribute to social progress, to create new things, to gain dominance and power over people's minds.

It is self-evident that young people and personal creativity show signs such as not being indifferent to the questions posed to them, shortcomings in thinking and work actions or conflicting information, trying to identify problems, and striving to find their solution based on the assumptions put forward.

So, to sum up, thinking creatively in young people creates the ground for not only their own lives, but also for them to be able to socialize and find their place in society correctly and at a high level. For this, we consider it appropriate to pay special attention to the following cases:

- encourage and support young people to ask many questions;
- to encourage the independence of young people and to strengthen and make them feel responsible;
- creating an opportunity and suitable environment for the organization of independent activities by young people;
- special attention to the interests of young people, etc.

At the same time, it is worth paying special attention to the following situations, which hinder the development of creativity. Including:

- risk-taking or exclusionary attitudes in young people;
- a state of rudeness or stubborn attitude in thinking and behavior of young people;
- high or inappropriate appreciation of youth fantasy and imagination;
- the subordination of young people to others or limiting themselves to only approving the opinions of others;
- young people think only of success in any case, and the extreme stuttering and babbling of defeat.

Therefore, based on the above conclusions, shaping how creatively our young people think and show an unconventional attitude towards existence is one of the main issues of today's society development.

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